

THE NEEDS TO DEVELOP A POSITIVE STUDENT DISCIPLINE MODEL THROUGH THE ASSESSMENT OF THE PROJECT FOR STRENGTHENING THE STUDENT'S PROFILE OF PANCASILA

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Abstract

It is important to develop positive discipline through assessment of the project for strengthening the student's profile of Pancasila (P5) so that students can form their character indirectly. The values of the P5, namely 1) have faith, be devoted to God Almighty, and have a noble character, 2) be independent, 3) work together, 4) global diversity, 5) critical reasoning, and 6) creative. This research aimed to describe developing a positive discipline model by assessing the project to strengthen the P5. The development of this positive discipline was through an assessment of the project to strengthen the P5 among students, especially phase E students at SMAN 1 Pulau Punjung so that they can form positive character. The research method was carried out using non-associative quantitative analysis with a sample of 73 students from a population of 268. Based on the needs analysis distributed through a questionnaire, it can be concluded that the development of a positive discipline model was needed according to the interest indicator reaching 90% in the very high category. Meanwhile, the needs indicator reached 89% in the high category.

Keywords: positive character, project assessment, P5

INTRODUCTION

Character formation starts from an early age to adolescence, which is influenced by several media, such as family, playmates, school, and society. Character is a way of thinking and behaving that is characteristic of each individual to live and work together, both within the family, community, nation, and state (Dewi et al., 2020).

Senior high school (SMA) students are teenagers who are greatly influenced by the school and community environment. The phenomenon that occurs is not obeying rules and regulations at school so many violations occur such as being late, not following lessons, lack of manners or ethics, damaging school

facilities, engaging in bullying behavior, and bullying.

The project for strengthening the student's profile of Pancasila (P5) is expected to form the personality of Indonesian students based on the values of Pancasila. One of the values contained in the P5 is an independent attitude (Sartika et al., 2023; Brata & Utomo, 2022; Nurhayati et al., 2022; Brata et al., 2022; Widarini & Suterji, 2023). However, the assessment of the project to strengthen the P5 can develop positive student discipline.

This project is a supporter of intracurricular activities that have the ultimate goal of not only increasing competence but also building and improving the character of students as P5 through

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the project which raises issues or problems in the surrounding environment (Fauziah & Rohmawati, 2023; Kusri, 2024; Ulum, 2023; Silviani et al., 2023). By developing character-based school discipline, students can learn to be more responsible, and honest, take initiative, and work well together. In the long term, students who have good character will be better able to face life's challenges and be successful in their careers (Sofyan & Wardani, 2016).

To overcome this problem, the approach usually taken by schools is to apply sanctions and punishments. However, this coaching is not always effective and can harm students. Therefore, there needs to be a more holistic approach to developing school discipline that can shape students' character positively. One approach that can be taken is the development of character-based school discipline and the development of child-friendly schools (SRA).

This approach emphasizes the formation of student character through the formation of a positive disciplinary attitude. By developing character-based school discipline, students can learn to be more responsible, honest, take initiative, and work well together. In the long term, students who have good character will be better able to face life's challenges and be successful in their careers (Sofyan & Wardani, 2016). In the context of educational psychology, positive character refers to students' ability to face difficulties, remain steadfast in making the right decisions, and be aware of their duties and responsibilities, which are important assets in managing themselves and social relationships.

The ability to think logically, critically, and creatively, as well as being able to regulate emotions and accept criticism are one of the positive characteristics that must be instilled in the world of education. Therefore, the educational psychology perspective presents strategies for facing challenges in building positive character in students. In the Regulation of the Minister of State for Women's Empowerment and Child Protection of the Republic of Indonesia Number 8 of 2014 concerning Child-Friendly School Policy, it is explained that in realizing Child-Friendly Schools (SRA) there are six indicators developed to measure SRA achievements.

These indicators are 1) SRA policy, 2)

curriculum implementation, 3) education and educational staff trained in child rights, 4) SRA facilities and infrastructure, 5) child participation, and 6) participation of parents, community institutions, the business world, other stakeholders, and alumni.

According to UNICEF in 2005, there six indicators must be met to realize SRA. The SRA model is not just an abstract concept or methodology. The SRA concept is an educational principle that recognizes that child-centered education is part of human rights. In principle, child-friendly schools are an important thing that must be created at all times. The SRA concept was created based on the principle of realizing children's rights to quality education. In this case, it is emphasized that creating decent schools is an important thing to do (Syahroni, 2021).

As for the results of free observations and interviews of students at SMAN 1 Pulau Punjung, there are several social phenomena in the school environment. Problems often faced by students include: students are often late, being absent without explanation, lack of manners, etc bullying between friends, lack of focus during the learning process in class, not complying with agreements regarding clothing, hair, shoes, attributes, and so on, fights that occur in the school environment.

From various problems related to the condition of student character at SMAN 1 Pulau Punjung, the author presents conclusions from these various problems based on the results of observations obtained from the principal, guidance and counseling educators, as well as subject educators who are equipped with observations of the participant's behavior. Students directly in terms of student activities outside the educational process, as well as in the teaching and learning educational process.

In this case, the author will develop a positive discipline model through an assessment co-curricular project strengthening the P5. In general, positive discipline is an approach to applying discipline from within the child without punishment or reward. Positive discipline needs to be applied both in the family environment and the school environment. By implementing positive discipline, it is hoped that acts of violence can be avoided.

The positive discipline approach is not about children/students directly, but rather how

adults can have a positive impact and influence on children/students. The positive discipline approach emphasizes a positive approach without violence, motivating, reflecting on mistakes, respecting, and building logic, and is long-term. As for discipline, positive is an approach to applying discipline from within students that aims to raise awareness and empower students to independently do things without punishment or reward.

The goal of positive discipline is to instill motivation to become the person they want to be and respect themselves with the values they believe in. Discipline positivity begins with motivation from within (intrinsic) participant education. Positive discipline emphasizes a positive approach without violence, motivating, reflecting on mistakes, respecting, and building logic, and is long-term. Examples of positive discipline at school include arriving on time, participating in learning activities, speaking politely, and respecting teachers and friends. Based on the researcher's observations and several literature, the research aimed to develop a positive discipline model for students through an assessment project strengthening Pancasila student profile (P5) at SMAN 1 Pulau Punjung.

METHOD

This research method was carried out using a non-quantitative method associative. This research was based on the results of a needs analysis. The focus of this research was on how to ensure students have positive discipline through assessment projects strengthening the P5. Technique data collection was carried out by distributing questionnaires or answering several questions in the needs analysis for phase E students at SMAN 1 Pulau Punjung.

In this research, a direct questionnaire was used with closed questions with answers to the questions asked and available. Sample The research numbered 73 people from 268 phase E students at SMAN 1 Pulau Punjung based on Formula (1).

$$n = \frac{N}{N \cdot d^2 + 1} \tag{1}$$

n = Sample size
 N = Population size
 d = Percentage of error allowance due to sampling (10%)

The data obtained will be analyzed based on a range of values with scoring which is seen in Table 1.

Table 1 Range of Value with Data Scoring

Range	Value
90-100	Very high
80-89	High
65-79	Medium
55-64	Low
0-54	Very Low

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Initial observations show that the majority of students feel forced to apply discipline positively in the assessment project strengthening the P5. The findings in this research showed that the majority of students have not applied positive discipline in assessment projects strengthening the P5. This indicates a match between student preferences and the development of the proposed positive discipline model. They showed very high interest and needs the development of positive student discipline models through assessment projects strengthening the P5.

One of the main founders of the concept of positive discipline defined positive discipline as a method of educating children that does not only focus on punishment or rewards but also teaches social and life skills (Nelsen, 1981). Positive discipline is based on mutual respect and encouraging children to understand the consequences of their actions, as well as helping them become responsible individuals and able to solve problems.

P5 is one of the efforts to improve the quality of education in Indonesia which prioritizes character formation. In the current era of technological advances in globalization, the role of values and character education is very much needed to provide a balance between technological development and human development (Faiz & Kurniawaty, 2022). Strengthening the P5 focuses on cultivating character and abilities in everyday life, instilled in individual students through school culture, learning intracurricular and extracurricular, a project to strengthen the profile of Pancasila students as well as work culture (Rahayuningsih, 2022).

Students showed a very high level of

interest and need for the development of positive discipline through the assessment of the project to strengthen the profile of Pancasila students. These findings may reflect that the development of positive discipline models can be an effective means of shaping student characteristics.

At the initial needs analysis stage, the research results identified concrete difficulties faced by students in developing positive discipline. For example, difficulties in learning projects to strengthen the P5 in character building. Researchers highlight how assessment in learning projects to strengthen the P5 can help students understand and form character student. Many things make students unable to develop positive discipline under the values of the P5. These things are caused by a lack of interest and needs of students, so they experience difficulties in learning the project to strengthen the P5.

Based on the problem above, the researcher obtained the results of observations on a needs analysis questionnaire distributed to students which contained two variables, namely interest and need for developing a positive discipline model through the assessment of the project to strengthen the P5. This needs analysis was researched based on the number of samples and population at SMA N 1 Pulau Punjung. This can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2 Population Number of Phase E Students of SMAN 1 Punjung Island Academic Year 2023/2024

Class	The Number of Students
Phase E1	35 students
Phase E2	34 students
Phase E3	35 students
Phase E4	34 students
Phase E5	33 students
Phase E6	34 students
Phase E7	34 students
Phase E8	29 students
Total	268 students

Table 2 showed the population from which the research sample will be taken. Through a needs analysis questionnaire consisting of two variables on students' interests and needs regarding the need to develop this positive discipline model through an assessment of the project to strengthen the

P5, then get it the results which is seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Needs Analysis

Figure 1 showed of the 16 questions given almost all students expressed interest and needs to develop this positive discipline model through the assessment of the project to strengthen the P5. In the interest variable, it can be seen that student interest was very high in developing this positive discipline model through assessing the project to strengthen the P5. Likewise with the needs variable, it can be seen that the need for students to develop this positive discipline model through the assessment of the project to strengthen the P5 was high. This showed that so far positive discipline has felt very forced and unattractive for students. The category was very low to moderate, no students answered it.

Based on the results, it can be concluded that research based on a needs analysis for the development of this positive discipline model through an assessment of the project to strengthen the P5 received a positive response from the students. They felt very interested and also felt the need to develop this positive discipline model by assessing the project to strengthen the P5. How to implement positive discipline at school, by explaining the four stages that need to be carried out in implementing positive discipline.

The first stage explains the conditioning stage where the conditioning stage can be carried out in several activities, such as socializing the positive discipline movement, facilitating the implementation of socialization, socializing positive implementation to stakeholders/parents, making a joint commitment in the form of signing an integrity pact, and carrying out problem mapping. The second stage explains the consolidation stage which aims to prepare the supporting capacity for implementing positive

discipline in schools. Several activities that need to be carried out at this stage, such as declarations of positive disciplinary movement, developing coping mechanisms, substantive training in the application of positive discipline, and workshops for parents. The third stage of implementing positive discipline. The implementation of positive discipline is characterized by coaching students by educators and educational staff with a mutual exchange of students, students' best books, or annual awards for students who excel (Nasution et al., 2023).

According to researchers, several things need to be developed to achieve a goal, such as socialization, agreement, habits, and positive discipline culture (Setyaputri, 2022; Syofiyanti & Marjuk, 2023; Masrurroh et al., 2022; Ilmiah, 2022; Khoeriyah, 2020; Aufa et al., 2022; Nisa et al., 2023; Sutarna et al., 2022; Ayni et al., 2022; Pribadi et al., 2021; Sobri et al., 2019; Murestiyanto, 2022; Taufik & Akip, 2021; Rosita et al., 2022). Socialization is a process of social interaction that causes an individual to know how to think, feel, and behave so that he can participate in social life. Socialization aims to shape individuals into responsible, independent members of society and productive. Implementation of socialization carried out during the admission of new students and the introduction period to the school environment.

A student agreement is an agreement that contains several rules agreed upon by the teacher and students to form effective teaching and learning activities. This agreement aims to create effective, comfortable, and enjoyable learning according to students' dreams. Implementation of student agreements at school in the form of attendance, cleanliness, collecting assignments, and student ethics. Habits are behaviors that are carried out continuously without going through a thought process because this behavior is a response to something that is generally an everyday action.

The purpose of this habit is to help students physically and mentally achieve goals and create better personal habits. Several implementation habits such as doing assignments, repeating lessons regularly, making study schedules, and implementing them, as well as good ethics and manners.

Positive discipline culture is a pattern or way of life that is developed by a group of students and then passed on to the next generation. The purpose of a positive disciplined culture is a guide relationships between humans or groups, to channel feelings and other lives, guide human life, and distinguish between humans and animals. An example of a positive discipline culture that creates a pattern of life that continues to be developed in the next generation.

CONCLUSION

The analysis test results obtained in this research showed that classical services and individual services have an influence on student motivation but the influence given to weak intervals and individual service variables did not have a significant influence. So it is necessary for guidance and counseling teachers at SMA Negeri 1 Pulau Punjung to look for other methods or models of guidance to increase students' motivation to continue to college. Apart from finding other methods and models of guidance, it is also necessary to look at other variables that are taken into consideration by guidance and counseling teachers in increasing their students' motivation, because the percentage influence of classical services and individual services only influences 32%, there are still many other variables that have not been studied.

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